

The Form of Nonrelativistic Kinetic Energy and Quantum Time-Space Resolution

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It is well-known that nonrelativistic kinetic energy is $p^2/2m$ which follows from a $v/c \ll 1$ expansion of the relativistic result $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. The Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ for a free particle in special relativity is also known. We have argued in the past that if dt and dx are independent, i.e. represent resolutions, then \hbar/E and \hbar/p represent these resolutions. These are the quantum resolutions. Regardless of whether they follow from $-Et + px$ or not, these may serve as nonrelativistic temporal and spatial resolutions if one uses $E = \text{kinetic energy}$.

We start with the nonrelativistic quantum resolutions \hbar/E and \hbar/p and the case of an infinite well potential governed by the time-independent Schrodinger equation. We assume that one does not know the form of $E(p)$ and ask whether quantum mechanics can yield it? We suggest it can in the following manner. A particle in the well has an average momentum and hence an average speed. This average speed is based on an x interval divided by a time interval because speed is constant. For the square well potential, x resolution must be equal or less than L , the length of the potential. Thus, to an extent one has a sense of the length of the potential region. If one considers the length L , then $L = v_{\text{ave}} T$, but the quantum resolution \hbar/E must be less than this value in order that such a time may be sensed. Otherwise, the notion of v_{ave} seems to make no sense. If $p = \hbar n \pi / L$, then T is proportional to LL/m and we argue that $1/E$ must also be proportional to these values in order that $T E$ contain no m and L and at the same time be greater than one for T to be resolved. This suggests that E is proportional to $1/m$ ($1/LL$) i.e. to p^2/m_0 . We go one step further and ask whether this form may shed light on special relativity and suggest that it might.

Quantum Mechanical Time and Spatial Resolution and the Notion of Velocity

In classical mechanics, velocity is a key value because one follows a particle in space and knows $x(t)$ for each t and x , i.e. there is infinite resolution for x and t . dx/dt is then velocity. The issue in quantum mechanics is that there is a spatial and time resolution for a free particle given by:

$$\text{Time resolution} = \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad \text{spatial resolution} = \hbar/p \quad ((1))$$

Here we consider nonrelativistic mechanics and so $E = p^2/2m_0$ and $p = m_0 v$ where m_0 is rest mass.

The issue we raise is that for a bound system, in particular the infinite well potential which has a sharply localized length L , the average momentum p_{ave} and E_{ave} should lead to time and spatial resolutions of:

$$\text{Time resolution} = \hbar/E_{\text{ave}} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{spatial resolution} = \hbar/p_{\text{ave}} \quad ((2))$$

At the same time, $v_{\text{ave}} = p_{\text{ave}}/m$ and there is a fixed length L , so:

$$L = \hbar v / m T \quad ((3))$$

In terms of spatial resolution, there is no issue because it must be of the order of L or smaller. Solving the time-independent Schrodinger equation for the well yields solutions of:

$$\sin(\hbar v x) \quad \text{for } x=0 \text{ to } x=L \quad \text{with } \hbar v = \hbar n \pi / L \quad ((4))$$

Thus, there is no issue in quantum mechanics with sensing the length L .

Next, assume that one does not know the math form of the energy E . We ask whether one may use quantum mechanical resolution to deduce its form.

$$\text{Given that } L = \hbar v / m T : \quad T = \hbar L / m (1 / (\hbar n \pi)) \quad ((5))$$

For the quantum system to be able to sense T , one requires that $T_{\text{quantum}} = \hbar / E$ be less than or equal to T . This suggests that values like L, m and π disappear. We use $c=1$ and $\hbar=1$ Thus:

$$E \text{ proportional to } 1 / (Lm) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{In other words } E \text{ is proportional to } p^2 / m \quad ((7))$$

This does not give the exact nonrelativistic form of E , but it does suggest its dependence on p and m .

The exact form of nonrelativistic kinetic energy follows from special relativity:

$$E^2 - p^2 = m^2 \quad \text{or } E \rightarrow m + KE \text{ so: } KE = p^2 / 2m \quad ((8))$$

((7)), however, partially anticipates this result through the use of quantum time and spatial resolutions, we suggest. We ask: Given the form ((7)) can one deduce any information about special relativity?

Quantum Nonrelativistic Spatial and Time Resolution and Special Relativity

In classical mechanics, $KE = p^2 / 2m$, in other words energy and p momentum are not on the same footing, i.e. are not part of a generalized vector.

If one considers the form p^2 / m from the idea of units, and assumes that m is proportional to energy then given that p^2 / m is energy, p^2 must be proportional to energy squared. This approach places p and energy on the same footing and in such a case one may obtain a form like ((7)) using:

$$(m_0 + KE)(m_0 + KE) = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad ((9))$$

This would then suggest that one has a kind of modulus (unusual metric) of a 4-vector (p, E) . Thus, the idea of nonrelativistic quantum spatial and temporal resolution could point to the form of special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that nonrelativistic quantum mechanical spatial and temporal resolution of a free particle or infinite square well potential, namely \hbar/E (where E is kinetic energy) or \hbar/p may be used to find a proportionality relation between E and p , namely E proportional to p^2/m . This follows from the temporal resolution being less than or equal to the time in $L = \hbar/pv$. If this is not the case, one cannot have any sense of T because the quantum temporal resolution is not good enough, hence there is no concept of v in L when there should be. We go further and argue that if one thinks of m_0 as energy, then p^2/m suggests that p should also be proportional to energy using the idea of units. (p would need to be multiplied by a constant.) This then leads to the idea of $E = m_0 + KE$ being the full energy being on the same footing as p , i.e. as in E and p being part of a vector which should have a modulus squared. This then would lead directly to the form: $KE = p^2/2m_0$ if $(m_0 + KE)(m_0 + KE) = p^2 + m_0^2$.